

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 2 ISSUE 1 (2023)

PUBLISHED BY
E-PALLI PUBLISHERS, DELAWARE, USA

Metacognitive Awareness and Attitude Towards Communicative Approach of Junior High School Students

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Article Information

Received: January 10, 2022

Accepted: January 13, 2023

Published: January 15, 2023

Keywords

*Education, Metacognitive
Awareness, Attitude,
Communicative Approach,
Correlation, Regression,
Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study aims to establish the significance of the influence of metacognitive awareness to the attitude towards communicative approach of Junior High School students. In order to do so, this study employed the quantitative research design using the descriptive and correlational method. Using proportionate stratified random sampling, primary data were gathered through the distribution of printed survey questionnaires inserted along with their English Modules as part of the Printed Modular-Based Learning Modality given to 369 respondents from 18 Secondary Public Schools of Division of Davao del Sur. In addressing the hypotheses of the study, correlation analysis using Pearson product moment correlation and regression analysis using Sobel z test were used. The level of metacognitive awareness as perceived by Junior High School students is high while the attitude towards communicative approach was defined as moderate. Results also revealed metacognitive awareness to have significant relationship to attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students. This implies that level of metacognitive awareness associates to the nature of attitude towards communicative approach. Moreover, regulation of cognition is the domain that best influences the attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students.

INTRODUCTION

In Philippines, English language classroom heavily focused on the grammatical component of the language. Often, students are asked to practice to master language rules and read from the textbooks. As the result, students have shown low proficiency in speaking even though they have good knowledge in vocabulary, grammar, and reading skill. Results of the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) in English subject among public high school students all over the division had been declining as the data shows from the Office of the Division of Davao del Sur ranging from 53%-72% as of 2020. Students' communicative ability has become a concern because many students do not show satisfying levels of proficiency in communication even after ten years of English language learning. A variety of issues have been identified as being responsible for poor speaking skills among language learners in general. Their English skills are still low (Soomro & Farooq, 2018). This issue on academic achievement is particularly true in the case of the Philippine basic education, as reflected in the overall performance of the high school students.

As the name implies, the Communicative Approach views language learning as a whole, utilizing a variety of situations to help students communicate effectively (Sabrina, 2020). Because its ideas reflect a communicative perspective of language learning, Communicative Language Teaching is considered an approach rather than a strategy. Brainstorming, information gap, role plays, think-pair-share, interviews, problem solving tasks, group discussion, jigsaws, games, challenges, and other well-known communicative activities are often used in Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) classrooms. Interactions, functions, meanings, dynamics, issues,

task orientation, and authenticity are connected with communication activities (Ho, 2020).

The significance of the relationship between metacognitive awareness and students' attitudes toward communicative approaches has been the subject of several studies in recent years. Thus, (Milenkovic, 2020) was able to demonstrate that there is a positive correlation between metacognitive awareness in writing and a communicative approach to teaching students. In addition, Takallou (2021) found that his research provided support for the strong relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude in the communicative approach. Hence, students play an essential part in the development of innovative pedagogical approaches; the primary objective of teachers should be to assist students in developing an awareness of various learning strategies and in applying these strategies effectively.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) aims to improve learners' communicative competence in listening, speaking, reading, writing, nonverbal interactions, and all other aspects of communicative competence. Students all demand grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, cultural awareness, social position, interpersonal skills, coherence, cohesiveness, background knowledge, and meanings beyond the sentences (Ho, 2020). However, speaking, which frequently needs them to express their thoughts orally, and other skills (Abrar *et al.*, 2018). Due to the obstacles, insufficient learning tools, and limited time and opportunity for practice, many students are rarely motivated to study English. They cannot communicate in English even in their daily life. Interacting in English class is even getting worse. They cannot convey their opinion or idea in total and complete sentences. If they can do it,

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it will show many more grammatical errors. Lastly, they are not eager to speak English. It is in this considerable magnitude that the researcher will find the conception of this study more than timely so as to immediately address the growing problems on the attitude towards communicative approach of high school students. Moreover, the desire to impart a contribution to enrich the English Department inspires the researcher to pursue the study.

This study aims to establish the significance of the influence of metacognitive awareness to the attitude towards communicative approach of Junior High School students. Additionally, the study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of metacognitive awareness among Junior High School students in terms of
 - 1.1 knowledge about cognition;
 - 1.2 regulation of cognition.
2. To measure the level of attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students in terms of
 - 2.1 general attitude;
 - 2.2 active engagement;
 - 2.3 speech confidence;
 - 2.4 learning; and
 - 2.5 behavioral intention?
3. To ascertain the significance of the relationship between metacognitive awareness and the attitude to the communicative approach Junior High School students.
4. To identify which domains of metacognitive awareness best influences the attitude of the Junior High School students towards communicative approach.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section comprises numerous reading, related literature, and studies to give a general idea of the current study. The independent variable is metacognitive awareness taken from Schraw, G. & Dennison, R.S. (1994) while the dependent variable is attitude towards communicative approach from Agbatogun (2013). The indicators of each variable is also discussed in depth in this section.

Metacognition is “reflecting on one’s cognition.” There are two components to metacognition: reflection, or the consideration of what we know, and self-regulation, or the management of how we learn. Collectively, these processes constitute an essential part of learning and growth. Improving metacognitive awareness is vital to the teaching-learning process. If the student knows how he learns, he can determine the most efficient methods. With this talent, students will be encouraged to consider how they will learn most effectively, fostering the development of an awareness skill (self-awareness) essential to learning. Using metacognition, a student may readily comprehend and evaluate any scenario and use the most effective strategies and procedures (Constantino, Sison and Guzman, 2020; Jaleel and P., 2016; Pahayahay and Cisneros-Pahayahay, 2017).

Learners who can use their knowledge and experience

to plan, assess, and adjust their problem-solving approach systematically engage in metacognition. This has the potential to improve student performance and make school more fun. It follows that pupils who lack metacognitive ability are less likely to employ effective learning strategies, which impairs their cognitive capacities (Abdelrahman, 2020; Erlin and Fitriani, 2019; Siqueira *et al.*, 2020).

They understand the learning process and applying that knowledge to completing tasks in everyday teaching and learning requires metacognitive skills. It also affects the learning outcomes, such as the student’s ability to think critically and solve problems independently. Students with solid metacognitive skills can better take charge of their education and form sound scientific theories. Furthermore, pupils who develop metacognitive awareness show considerable improvement in their problem-solving skills. A person with this metacognitive skill could improve their ability to learn and solve problems, make plans, and think critically (Alindra, Fauzan and Asmar, 2018; DHYANI and MAIKHURI, 2018; Hassan *et al.*, 2022).

Students that have a variety of various learning trajectories require a variety of different forms of help to develop a metacognitive knowledge of their learning processes. In this sense, metacognition can be understood as individual self-regulation. The operations that move information from one information repository to another are directed and controlled by it. To foster metacognitive awareness in students and give them the tools they need to become self-directed learners, teachers must consciously decide when to pull back on their involvement in the learning process and put students in the driver’s seat of the educational experience (Bergil, 2021; Kaur, 2020; Tuononen *et al.*, 2022).

In a similar vein, learning in humans relies heavily on a process known as metacognition. Students with high metacognitive awareness are aware of what they are expected to achieve in this assignment. They find that it is easier to complete, particularly when they are given more opportunities to work together. It is important to note that how students view a task following the learning circumstance can foretell the consequences of the student’s learning. In addition, increased metacognitive awareness was critical in improving students’ writing performance by lowering the amount of anxiety they felt during writing activities. This was accomplished by enhancing students’ ability to plan and organize their writing. By instructing the participant in the metacognitive planning approach on the metacognitive awareness strategy before student learning, this technique has been shown to benefit the level of writing achievement. The student’s ability to learn new terminology was also aided by their metacognitive awareness and connectivist learning (Aglina *et al.*, 2020; Çini, Malmberg and Järvelä, 2020; Poo and Funn, 2017). Learning is metacognitively guided, intrinsically motivated, and strategically oriented in the context of self-regulated learning. Those with a higher degree of metacognitive awareness also have a greater tendency to perform academically compared to students with a

lower degree of metacognitive awareness. The ability of learners to reflect on their thinking and exert control over their cognitive processes is a crucial element of metacognitive instruction. Therefore, to complete a learning activity, they need to be conscious of the mental processes they are engaging in and be able to self-regulate those processes (Savitri and Anam, 2018; Siqueira *et al.*, 2020; Ward and Butler, 2019).

Students can increase self-awareness with a thinking diary. Writing about the day's events can help teachers assess students' learning and comprehension. Students should review previous content before going on. Sessions start with a "what do I want?" check-in. Students must assess their knowledge. Students may manage their time, complete assignments on time, build a study strategy, evaluate their success, and alter the curriculum as needed. Cognitive and metacognitive skills "drive" students' thoughts. Metacognition is self-aware learning. Teachers of average to below-average intelligence kids should promote self-awareness. These skills should boost academic performance (Dr. Neena Sawhney and Dr. Sneha Bansal, 2015; Hindun, Nurwidodo and Wicaksono, 2020; Zulkiply, 2020).

Metacognition refers to the awareness of one's thought process and the ability to control that process. Training can be used to improve one's metacognitive capabilities. Teaching students about metacognition and the necessity of lifelong learning, as well as making teachers aware of the significance of metacognition, can assist students in developing the ability to teach themselves how to learn. It is possible to suggest that kids' ability to make decisions can be set during primary education when teachers get children involved in activities to develop their metacognitive awareness. Therefore, prior preparation and understanding of the conditions involved may predict learning success. Teachers are strongly encouraged to assist students in developing their metacognitive awareness, that is, to expect students to establish objectives for their education (Akaydin, Yorulmaz and Çokçalışkan, 2020; Kallio, Virta and Kallio, 2018; Omprakash *et al.*, 2021).

Students should be taught "learning to learn," a paradigm shift from traditional to real learning. Metacognition is key to lifelong learning. Teachers should be aware of the importance of embedding metacognitive education in teaching, as this will help students gain conditional metacognitive knowledge as they are exposed to a variety of scenarios demanding metacognitive and cognitive skills. Metacognitive skills should be included in curriculum and learning strategies to enable students to monitor and regulate their learning to face academic society's challenges. Furthermore, metacognitive awareness helps students appraise the task, design a strategy, use selected tactics, monitor progress, evaluate, and alter their techniques (ELIAS, 2020; Pradhan* and Das, 2021; Sonowal and Kalita, 2017).

Metacognition instruction is undervalued in educational policy and practice. Educating metacognitive folks is crucial to developing autonomous learners who think, act,

take a stand, and make reasoned decisions. Metacognition helps English primary school instructors articulate higher-order cognitive processes practiced in reading comprehension instruction. Real-world experiences are another way to increase students' metacognitive awareness and learning motivation. With allows teachers to monitor, analyze, and adapt their instructional approaches based on students, goals, and settings. For enables teachers to create instruction that develops and activates students' metacognition, allowing them to be aware of what they know and don't know and to rectify errors or gaps in their knowledge (Esref and Cevat, 2021; Nordin and Yunus, 2020; O'Hara, Pritchard, and Pitta, 2019).

To synthesize all of the relevant reviews that have been offered in this study, it can be said that students' metacognitive awareness is significant in their learning. It is a significant factor that can be used to characterize one's overall academic achievement. When pupils have a high level of metacognitive awareness, it allows them to perform very well in their academic pursuits. Therefore, teachers are being pushed to instruct pupils in a manner that is more realistic so that the students may participate. Hence, for pupils to develop higher-order thinking skills, teachers need to be very effective in directing the teaching-learning process. Students are exposed to critical thinking and can make good decisions when given this opportunity.

The communicative approach was introduced in Asia in the 1970s, but it was not until the late 1980s and early 1990s that it became the focus of attention; this was most likely due to a significant gap between its primary focus on communicative competence and the traditional way of teaching in many parts of Asia, which emphasizes language forms and grammatical rules. The communicative approach, which was founded on a solid theoretical foundation, was widely accepted by British language teaching professionals, curriculum planners, textbook writers, and even the government. It has quickly been adopted and expanded in the world of second and foreign language teaching, to improve learners' communicative competence. Furthermore, the study's findings revealed that students in the study area have favorable attitudes toward the communicative approach. However, they are not eager to work in pairs or groups (Nisrane and Dengela, 2019; IWAMOTO, 2017; Khatib and Ashoori Tootkaboni, 2019).

The majority of researchers who addressed this issue reported that the majority of learners have favorable attitudes toward communicative approaches. Besides, another study found some disagreements between learners' and teachers' attitudes toward the role of explicit grammar teaching in general and error correction in particular. While students were generally in favor of an explicit focus on form and error correction, their teachers had a more mixed reaction. The deeply ingrained belief in the importance of learning structural aspects of language as a foundation of language learning influenced learners. Students have a strong positive attitude toward the

communicative teaching approach's suggested classroom activities. It is suggested that using role-playing, group discussions, and video production can help students gain confidence while also improving their listening and speaking skills (IWAMOTO, 2017; Khatib and Ashoori Tootkaboni, 2019; Komol and Suwanphathama, 2020).

Attitudes appear to influence whether students achieve communicative competence, highlighting the importance of attitudes in language learning. A person's thoughts regarding their own or other people's languages are referred to as their attitude toward a language. Learners will be content if they have positive attitudes toward language development. Positivity improves language abilities. Students' impressions are harmed by negative attitudes. Furthermore, a person speaks to affect the conduct, thoughts, and feelings of others through speaking activity. Thus, modeling, repetition, pair and group work are the key tactics utilized by teachers to help students (Alibekova and Urinboeva, 2020; Fabian, 2019; Losi and Nasution, 2022).

The communicative approach first emerged in the 70s as a result of the work of experts from the Council of Europe and since then has become widespread throughout the world and has become one of the main methods of teaching foreign languages. Moreover, the communicative approach is probably the most popular in recent English language teaching all over the world. Emphasizing communicative competence is one of the most influential developments in language education. Students do not know how to communicate outside the classroom in real-life situations, using the appropriate social language. While using this approach, the major focus is to make the learner able to communicate in the target language. Errors are tolerated by the teacher because what is more important is to make them able to speak in the target language. The teacher should not correct them during the activities in which they are using the target language. The teacher can note the errors of the learners and make them correct after the activities are over (Sayera, 2019; Pavlovna, 2020; Rahmawati, 2018).

The communicative approach is founded on the premise that engaging in activities is the best way to learn English. When learners replicate real-life situations, their motivation for language increases, allowing them to learn the language quickly and easily. It is therefore recommended that teachers employ the communicative language teaching technique to instill confidence in their pupils since this will allow them to improve their linguistic skills more quickly, as this approach prioritizes listening and speaking skills over reading and writing skills. Hence, when teachers use the communicative approach, pupils do better. As a result, the communicative approach takes the lead over traditional techniques (for example, grammatically translational) in the methodology of teaching foreign languages because of its practicality, variety, and productivity (Akanbi and Ndid, 2020; ристг and Khrystych, 2020; B and I., 2020).

Due to linguistics' pragmatic approach, especially the

theory of speech acts, interest in language's communicative role has grown. Learners must not only create grammatically correct sentences but also gain additional abilities to use the language effectively in studying or working situations. The communicative strategy depends on the educational program, goals, instructional content, and plan adjustment. The operational program that suits this form of teaching is the one that contains language exercises that affect the learners. Students need to develop a statement after understanding a text, a circumstance, or someone else's reality. Speaking is not perceived or planned as a repeat or replication of dialogues, but as a conscious activity, such as in a discussion, identifying and bringing an argument, or convincing or refuting the interlocutor (BINDILEU, 2019; Maulana, Musthafa and Hayati, 2020; Pidaeva, 2022).

Speaking proficiency is regarded as one of the essential language skills, with learners considered successful when they can use what they learn to communicate effectively. However, due to a lack of exposure to communication situations, many English as a foreign language (EFL) students struggle to master this ability. As a result, communicative activities had a significant impact on experimental students' speaking performance. And besides, students expressed positive attitudes toward the use of communicative activities in their speaking classrooms. Furthermore, by using the Communicative Language Approach, the students' achievement has improved. A survey of students in a study revealed a positive attitude toward using CLA to improve their speaking skills. The growing demand for fluent communication skills in today's globalized world makes foreign language teaching difficult. Students must be taught the communication skills that are required in various interactive real-world situations outside of the classroom. Students must be prepared for real-life scenarios rather than just passing a superficial paper exam. Because this is the primary goal of the communicative approach, students can gain communicative competence for social purposes (AlAdl, 2017; Kurniawan and Sumani, 2022; Vo, 2022).

On the other hand, there were discovered to be substantial disparities in the perspectives and attitudes of the students about the utilization of communicative activities. Students' perspectives about languages do have an impact on how well they learn such languages. Students may be influenced by these attitudes to learn or not learn the required amount of English language in the manner that is required. In addition, a lack of self-assurance is one of the reasons why students choose not to participate in language learning activities. Moreover, overcoming hurdles in the classroom, such as the number of students in each class, the learners' exam, and others should be a priority (Getie, 2020; Rezalou and Yagiz, 2021; Sholeh, Salija, and Sahril, 2021).

As can be seen from the review that was just presented, one of the most important factors in determining how well students learn a language is how well they can

communicate in that language. It is also obvious that the communicative approach is a useful method for improving one's ability to speak a language. This method is founded on the utilization of language in the context of learning topics as well as in real-life scenarios. Using the target language in their field topics and issues may give students the autonomy and self-confidence to pursue their interests. Students are finally able to achieve mastery of the most important skills that are associated with the English language. These skills include academic terms, language structure, and communication idioms.

Correlation Between Measures

The significance of the relationship between metacognitive awareness and students' attitudes toward communicative approaches has been the subject of several studies in recent years. Thus, Milenkovic was able to demonstrate that there is a positive correlation between metacognitive awareness in writing and a communicative approach to teaching students. In addition, Takallou found that his research provided support for the strong relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude in the communicative approach. Hence, students play an essential part in the development of innovative pedagogical approaches; the primary objective of teachers should be to assist students in developing an awareness of various learning strategies and in applying these strategies effectively.

In a similar vein, Tamin and Büyukahska found that students most frequently used strategies for problem-solving, followed by global strategies, and then support reading strategies. All of these strategies were used more frequently than support reading strategies. Therefore, the extent to which students are aware of their own metacognitive processes is a significant factor in determining the students' attitudes toward communicative approaches. In addition, the findings of research conducted by Thawarom *et al.* suggest that it is essential to improve one's metacognitive knowledge in order to successfully complete learning tasks in communicative competence.

According to Sulistyowati *et al.*, researchers investigate the impact of metacognition on the achievement of language learners and report that metacognition positively influences learners' learning achievement. Corollary to this, Bessy and Knouse argued that it is imperative for educators of foreign languages to foster student growth in metacognitive abilities and metalinguistic awareness, as well as to explicitly instruct students on the relevance of language learning study. Consequently, Miller reported that metacognitive reading strategies and conscious attention to reading are some of the primary contributors to language learners' reading comprehension. This is due to the fact that readers are able to become autonomous if they are aware of which strategy works for them to accomplish their goals in a more timely manner.

Moreover, Frith concluded that students' communication abilities depend heavily on their level of metacognitive awareness. Students are allowed to maximize the sharing of resources as well as the sharing of information thanks

to this. Concurrently, participation in social interactions has been shown to improve metacognition. Students can increase their capacity to provide a more accurate report on the reasons for their actions and experiences by participating in discussions with other students. In addition, metacognitive awareness plays a crucial part in communication, the ability to comprehend what is read, the acquisition of language, the ability to solve problems, and the development of personality (Gopinath). Furthermore, the results of several studies have shown that there is a positive association between the regulation of cognition and the components that make up it, as measured by language learning scores in writing. This indicates that authors with higher levels of expertise have a greater capacity to control and organize their thoughts and behaviors concerning the writing tasks they do (Farahian and Avarzamani).

Thus, it is essential to investigate metacognitive awareness and development to discover how students might be instructed to make better use of their cognitive resources by exercising metacognitive control (OZ). The range of correlation values shows that there is a considerable and very strong association between metacognitive awareness variables and the capacity of students to compose explanatory text as a communicative strategy by a teacher. This is evidenced by the value of 0.812 for the correlation range. The ability to compose explanatory language is influenced by metacognitive awareness by a factor of 66%, while other factors are responsible for the remaining 44% of the influence. This demonstrates that having metacognitive awareness plays a significant role in the writing process. Students are expected to continually raise their level of metacognitive awareness (Ramadhanti and Yanda).

The critical function that metacognitive awareness plays in the acquisition of a language, in particular the acquisition of listening and speaking skills in which the processes, even though they are dynamic and strategic, are not always visible to the learner (Goh). Communicative strategies can be said to have a connection to the notion of metacognition in the sense that language learners who use a communicative approach may be more or less aware of their language behavior (Bohn and Myklevold 180–198). In this sense, the communicative approach may be considered to be related to the concept of metacognition. Consequently, the correlation between these two variables that were shown in this research study may be considered solid evidence to prove that a relationship between metacognitive awareness and students' attitudes toward the communicative approach does exist. This would further mean that students need to have a metacognitive awareness to speak, communicate, and write effectively. Therefore, having a strong metacognitive awareness is extremely important in the field of communication. If they did not have access to it, students would struggle to communicate knowledge to one another, resulting in poor academic performance. As a result, it is recommended that careful consideration be given to this essential factor

to guarantee that students will have a good degree of communication skills.

Theoretical Framework

The challenges in the study were approached using a variety of ideas. The foundations of this research study include theories of metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach. Thus, the following two theories addressed these issues.

To begin, Takallou concluded his research that metacognitive awareness and attitude play a significant role in the communicative approach. This would also imply that children need to master these vital capabilities to participate in activities including speaking and writing. In addition, to inspire students, teachers need to be wise in how they moderate the abilities that are necessary for a student to develop. The students need to be encouraged to talk about their thoughts while the teachers are leading them in their discussion. They will be able to improve themselves as communicators, which is the primary goal of the communicative approach, by learning how to communicate effectively using this method.

Russell's Theory of Knowledge underpins metacognition. Doubt created the Theory of Knowledge. When we ask ourselves if we know anything, we examine our knowledge to separate trustworthy from untrustworthy views. Truth and error are distinguished. He then described knowledge as belief, words, belief and behavior, logic truth, uncertainty, and ambiguity. Hence, all these aspects are vital for students to know, especially in communication. This is supported by Sutiyatno who claimed that metacognitive awareness is a significant factor when is correlated to the reading achievement of students. Then, Flavell expounded that metacognitive awareness track cognitive improvement. Metacognitive techniques are ordered procedures used to govern one's own cognitive operations and ensure a cognitive goal (such as communicating with classmates, solving a math issue, writing a good sentence or understanding reading material) is reached. Good metacognitive skills and awareness let a person control his own learning, organize and monitor cognitive activities, and compare cognitive outcomes with internal or external norms.

The theory of knowledge is partly logical and partly psychological, yet these aspects aren't closely related. The logical part may come to organize knowledge according to degrees of certainty: some of our views include problematic assumptions. Logic, mathematics, and perception facts have the most certainty; memory and unseen matter have less certainty; beyond these levels, a prudent scientist would admit to uncertainty. The attempt to strengthen scientific certainty through philosophy seems impossible since philosophical propositions are among the most uncertain to which serious students offer unconditional assent (Russell).

Thus, attitude towards communicative approach is based on Bandura's social cognitive theory wherein we have an agentic conceptual framework within which to analyze the

determinants and psychosocial mechanisms through which symbolic communication influences human thought, affect and action. This conceptual framework was developed so that we could use it to examine these factors. This provides additional evidence in favor of the notion that metacognitive awareness is an essential skill. In his social cognitive theory of human functioning, self-beliefs are given a lot of weight, which highlights how crucial they are to human cognition, motivation, and behavior.

This is supported by Levitas and Hurst who stressed out a more specific classroom example to help make this point clearer. In the classroom as a teacher presents a lesson to the class, students reflect on what the teacher is saying. This is where the environment influences cognition, a personal factor. Students who don't understand a point raise their hands to ask a question. This is where personal factors influence behavior. So, the teacher reviews the point (behavior influences environment). Thus, Lazaro added that in social cognitive theory, the self-system is given a key role, which highlights the ability of individuals to exert some degree of control over their thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. Invariably, these two premises constitute to the reliability of the study for they met a school ground by which the assumption of this study is anchored on.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework showing the variables of the study. The independent variable of this research focuses on the Metacognitive Awareness which is depicted by the indicators namely: knowledge about cognition and regulation of cognition. Knowledge about cognition refers to the information students already know about themselves while regulation of cognition refers to the ability to organize, monitor, regulate, and evaluate the learning process.

The dependent variable of the study is Attitude towards Communicative Approach which is measured in terms of general attitude, active engagement, speech confidence, learning and behavioral intention. General attitude refers to the caring attitude over something or someone; active engagement refers to the readiness of students' interaction in learning; speech confidence refers to speaking with confidence and clarity; learning refers to the acquisition of knowledge or skills through experience, study, or by being taught; and behavioral intention refers to the motivational factors that influence a given behavior where the stronger the intention to perform the behavior, the more likely the behavior will be performed.

Diagram shows how metacognitive awareness predicts communicative approach attitude. This study model showed the association between two variables

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables using a single-headed arrow. Simple linear regression was used to determine the association between metacognitive awareness and communication approach. Regression analysis builds a model from two or more variables. Linear regression presupposes a proportional relationship

between variables based on linear correlation. Simple linear regression predicts one variable from another (Bazdaric *et al.*). In most cases, the variables will be designated as either dependent or independent. A

dependent variable, which is also sometimes referred to as an outcome, is affected by a set of inputs, drivers, or factors that are collectively referred to as independent variables (Ali and Younas).

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables

METHODOLOGY

This study employed quantitative approach, using correlation technique design to assess the relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach. Descriptive non-experimental correlational design controlled the extent of a relationship between two or more variables (Goertzen, 2017). In this study, correlation method is the best design to meet the objectives of this study and in finding out whether the hypothesis is accepted or not. Now, if the significance value is greater than .05, then, it means that H_0 is accepted and H_a is accepted. In fact, the testing of the hypothesis determines if the correlations can be strong or weak (Creswell, 2012).

Further it is a fact-finding study that allowed the researcher to examine characteristics, behaviors, and experiences of study participants (Calmorin, 2007). The study is descriptive in nature since it assessed the levels of metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach. This is correlational since it investigated the relationship between variables such as metacognitive awareness and students' attitude towards communicative approach with the use of the survey questionnaire as a tool in gathering the primary data. The interest of the study is to investigate the relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach. Regression analysis will be employed in determining the predicted variable of metacognitive awareness.

This academic undertaking involved Junior High School students of 18 Secondary Schools of Division of Davao del Sur. The total estimated number of respondents in this study is 4,819 Junior High School students, 369 of which were taken as sample size of the study. The research subjects of this study were evaluated using the validated research instrument. The respondents of this study were chosen as per official list of the school's registrar among all students who are currently enrolled in the junior high school level as the researcher wants to

find out the metacognitive awareness and the attitude to the communicative approach.

This study used the probability stratified sampling technique which cover selected Junior High School students in the secondary schools of the Division of Davao del Sur. The sample size calculator Raosoft (<http://www.raosoft.com/samplesize.html>) was used to determine the sample size of the respondents in order to conduct a reliability test of the instrument for final survey. Stratified random sampling divide the population into mutually exclusive groups in which random samples are taken. This was used to assure equal proportionate representation per secondary public schools that constitute the total sample size (Rahi 2017). Further, the respondents were able to understand the content of the survey questionnaire and they had the capacity to interpret based on their experiences in the school setting. In selecting the respondents, however, those who are dropped out and who have not enrolled shall not be part of the sample. Those who opt not to participate in the study for any reason may withdraw at any time and discontinue participation without penalty.

The survey questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part was intended for the profile of the respondents as well as the direction on how to rate the questions given. The second part includes specific items about the metacognitive awareness of Junior High School students which consisted two (2) indicators with an acceptable reliability score as follows: knowledge about cognition ($\alpha=.537$) and regulation of cognition ($\alpha=.506$). The survey instrument is an adopted test questionnaire developed by Schraw, G. & Dennison, R.S. (1994). Moreover, the scale used a 5-point Likert-type with options ranging from very high to very low. The degree of responses was then categorized and interpreted as follows.

The third part of the survey instrument consists items with regards to attitude towards communicative approach adapted from Alaba Agbatogun, (2013). The scale for service performance was taken from the SERVPERF

Range of Means	Description	Interpretations
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Measures of metacognitive awareness are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Measures of metacognitive awareness are often manifested.
2.40 – 3.39	Moderate	Measures of metacognitive awareness are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Measures of metacognitive awareness are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Measures of metacognitive awareness never manifested.

Range of Means	Description	Interpretations
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Measures of attitude towards communicative approach are always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Measures of attitude towards communicative approach are often manifested.
2.40 – 3.39	Moderate	Measures of attitude towards communicative approach are sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Measures of attitude towards communicative approach are seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Measures of attitude towards communicative approach never manifested.

model developed by Cronin and Taylor (1992). There are five indicators under this variable with an acceptable reliability score as follows: general attitude ($\alpha=.509$), learning ($\alpha=.720$), active engagement ($\alpha=.487$), speech confidence ($\alpha=.512$), and behavioral intention ($\alpha=.654$). A 5-point Likert-type scale rating is used as basis in the interpretation of data obtained from the responses in the instrument. The table below shows the rating scale for attitude towards communicative approach consisting of the range of means, description, and interpretation.

Refinement of the questionnaires was done through the assistance of the adviser and four validators who ensured its validity with an overall mean score of 4.17 assessed to be excellent. Before administering the questionnaire, the researcher conducted a pilot test to thirty (30) junior high school students to assess the suitability and coherence of the instrument. The research instruments were subjected to Cronbach Alpha Test for reliability testing, results of which are discussed in the subsequent paragraphs.

Due to Covid '19 pandemic, distribution of printed questionnaires to the prospective respondents was challenging. The secondary public schools in the Division of Davao del Sur adapted the Printed Modular-Based Learning Modality wherein students were given modules to be answered in a specific time and then submit them by schedule. The researcher tapped the English coordinators in the respective schools to allow me send the survey questionnaires along with the students' modules during the distribution in their school and assured to collect as well the survey instruments during the collection of learning modules. During the conduct of the survey, respondents were asked to read and answer the questions honestly and religiously.

Prior to distribution of survey instruments, the researcher sent letters of permission to conduct the study, signed by the adviser and favorably endorsed by the Dean of the Professional Schools to the school heads of eighteen (18) secondary schools. Strict compliance to health protocols were observed as I entered the school premises. School heads and principals allowed me to talk to the English coordinator and discuss further details regarding the process of survey instruments since students were not in their face-to-face learning set-up. The researcher conducted the study in January 2021 and retrieved the survey instruments in April 2021; there was a little delay

due to the circumstance that the researcher was tested positive and that required almost a month of home quarantine and observations. After retrieval, the responses were tabulated and processed using appropriate statistical tools. The tabulated data was analyzed and interpreted in accordance with the problem statements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Metacognitive Awareness

Shown in Table 1 is the descriptive statistics results in measuring the level of metacognitive awareness among Junior High School students. Overall mean of the level of metacognitive awareness among students is 3.81 (SD=.506), assessed to be high. The high level is reflective of high levels of its indicators, to include knowledge about cognition (M=3.85, SD=0.537) with a descriptive level of high and regulation of cognition (M =3.76, SD=0.536) with a descriptive level of high.

It can be gleaned from Table 1 that knowledge about cognition has more apparent manifestation of metacognitive awareness among students, however, very little difference in the ratings can be seen between the two indicators. Thus, the high level of all measures indicates that students often manifest or perform all dimensions of metacognitive awareness almost all the time, if not always. The level of metacognitive awareness as perceived by Junior High School students is high. Statistically, the two indicators knowledge about cognition and regulation of cognition are all described as high and this would have further empirical implication that students have used the highest level of wisdom in their studies. Moreover, knowledge about cognition has more apparent manifestation of metacognitive awareness among students which means that Junior High School students are aware about the knowledge they have within themselves, what they do not know and what to know in the future. Thus, the following indicators are presented from highest to the lowest scores.

These findings are in agreement with the findings of the research conducted by Constantino, Sison, and Guzman(2020) who discovered that enhancing metacognitive awareness is essential to the process of teaching and learning. If the student is aware of his learning style, he will be able to select the strategies that will be most helpful to him. In addition, Hassan *et*

al. (2022) noted that students who gain metacognitive awareness demonstrate a significant improvement in their ability to solve problems. A person who possesses this metacognitive capacity could boost their learning and problem-solving abilities, as well as their ability to plan and think critically.

The high-level of knowledge about cognition supports the qualitative evidence of Chen (2020) who shows improvements in cognitive awareness with students demonstrating a more consistent application of thinking skills, an increased ability to think critically with thinking dispositions cultivated, and most importantly, a transfer

Table 1: Level of Metacognitive Awareness of Junior High School Students

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
knowledge about cognition	3.85	.537	High
regulation of cognition	3.76	.536	High
Overall	3.81	.506	High

of thinking behavior across the curriculum and in their personal lives. Anthonysamy (2021) contended that students need to practice on how to utilise metacognitive strategies to enhance students' learning performance as those lacking in metacognition may find themselves at a huge disadvantage.

On the other hand, the high-level of regulation of cognition is parallel to a study of Sumarno *et al.* (2021) who confirmed that a student with good metacognitive skills will have good self-regulated learning skills, which enable him to establish reasonable writing goals, plan and strategies, which as a consequence, will improve his writing skills. Corrolary to this, Bártolo-Ribeiro *et al.* (2020) provided evidence that regulation of cognition is assumed to be more relevant for academic purposes. This is because it enables students to be aware of their own behaviors of planning before to carry out the tasks, the choice and monitoring of strategies during the learning process, and assessment attitudes of their learning process and learning outcomes.

Level of Attitude towards Communicative Approach

Table 2 presents the list of items in the six indicators of the level of attitude towards communicative approach that include general attitude, learning, active engagement, speech confidence and behavioral intention. As seen in Table 2, the overall mean of the level of attitude towards communicative approach is 3.36 (SD=0.399), assessed to be moderate. The moderate level could be attributed to the predominantly moderate ratings given to the indicators, to include learning (M=3.80, SD=0.720) with a descriptive level of high, special confidence (M=3.44, SD=0.512) with a descriptive level of high, behavioural intention (M=3.39, SD=0.654) with a descriptive level of moderate, active engagement (M=3.37, SD=0.487) with a descriptive level of moderate and general attitude (M=2.80, SD=0.509) with a descriptive level of moderate. Taken as a whole, it is surmised that students are

fairly inclined towards learning (M=3.80, SD=0.720), and special confidence (M=3.44, SD=0.512), which appeared to be high. The high level of learning and special confidence mean that these dimensions are more pronounced compared to three other indicators of attitude towards communicative approach among students. An overall moderate rating is indicative that students have different inclinations pertaining to their attitude towards communicative approach. The other variable considered in this study is attitude towards communicative approach which was defined as moderate. This would imply that inclinations relating communicative approach are not completely manifested by the student-respondents. Learning and speech confidence appeared to be in a high level which means that these dimensions are more pronounced compared to three other indicators of attitude towards communicative approach. Among the five indicators, learning garnered the highest score which indicates that Junior High School students show more positive response when exposed to varieties of pair work and group tasks.

These findings are in agreement with the research that was carried out by Komol and Suwanphathama (2020), which indicated that learners' deeply established beliefs about the significance of acquiring structural features of language as a basis for language learning influenced their language acquisition. Fabian (2019) elaborated on the concept of a person's attitude toward a language, defining it as a set of beliefs about one's language or the language of other people, and defining speech confidence as the conviction that one can utter the words one has in mind. Moreover, AlAdl (2017) posits that being able to communicate successfully in a foreign language is one of the most important indicators of a successful education. Vo's findings (2022) stress the need of students being ready for real-world events, not simply for a superficial paper exam. The communicative method aims to help students develop their communication skills for everyday social interactions.

Table 2: Level of Attitude towards Communicative Approach among Junior High School Students

Indicators	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
general attitude	2.80	.509	moderate
learning	3.80	.720	High
active engagement	3.37	.487	moderate
speech confidence	3.44	.512	High
behavioural intention	3.39	.654	moderate
Overall	3.36	.399	moderate

Correlation between Metacognitive Awareness and the Attitude towards Communicative Approach among Junior High School Students

Displayed in Table 3 are the results of the pairwise correlation analysis via Pearson product moment correlation test. The overall result of the level of attitude towards communicative approach and the level of metacognitive awareness among students yielded an r-value of 0.471 with a probability value of $p < 0.000$, which is significant at 0.05 level. This means that there is a significant relationship between attitude towards communicative approach and metacognitive awareness among Junior High School Students. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the level of attitude towards communicative approach and the level of metacognitive awareness among students is rejected.

Based on the analyses, overall attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students significantly relates with knowledge about cognition ($r = 0.415, p < 0.05$) and regulation of cognition ($r = 0.474, p < 0.05$) which posted strong correlation. So the indicators of personal metacognitive awareness mainly affect their attitude towards communicative approach among students. This indicates a direct or positive

relationship, thus, null hypothesis is rejected. All in all, the positive coefficients indicate a possible increment of dependent variables when independent variables increase, which will be confirmed in a subsequent regression analysis.

The test of relationship between variables reveals that there is a significant relationship between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students. This implies that level of metacognitive awareness associates to the nature of attitude towards communicative approach. This indicates that the character of one's attitude toward the method of communication is related to their level of metacognitive awareness. In contrast, this study lends credence to the work of Milenkovic (2020), who showed that a communicative approach to the classroom is correlated favorably with students' metacognitive awareness in writing. In addendum, this is in line with the premise of Takallou (2021) who discovered a strong connection between metacognitive awareness and attitude in the communication approach. This means that students should actively involved in the design of new pedagogical methods and that teachers should make it their top priority to help their students become aware of and proficient in a variety of learning tactics.

Table 3: Correlation matrix showing the results of the test of significant relationship between Metacognitive Awareness and Attitude towards Communicative Approach

Attitude towards Communicative Approach	Metacognitive Awareness		
	knowledge about cognition	regulation of cognition	Overall
general attitude	.173**(.001)	.220**(.000)	.208**(.000)
learning	.399**(.000)	.415**(.000)	.431**(.000)
active engagement	.357**(.000)	.424**(.000)	.414**(.000)
special confidence	.376**(.000)	.403**(.000)	.412**(.000)
behavioral intention	.129*.013	.185**(.000)	.166**(.001)
Overall	.415**(.000)	.474**(.000)	.471**(.000)

Significance on the Influence of the Indicators of Metacognitive Awareness on Overall Attitude towards Communicative Approach

Shown in Table 4 is the result of the regression analysis showing the predictive ability of the indicators of metacognitive awareness on overall attitude towards communicative approach among students. The computed R^2 value of 0.229 and adjusted R^2 of 0.225 means that 22.5 to 22.9 percent of the variance of attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School

Students can be attributed to the entry of the two metacognitive awareness indicators.

This means further that 77.1 to 77.5 percent of the remaining variance can be further attributed to other variables not covered in the study. In addition, the F-measure of the regression analysis is 54.805, $p < 0.01$. The result is significant that resulted to the rejection of the null hypothesis of no linear association between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach.

Table 4 : Domain of Metacognitive Awareness that best influences Attitude towards Communicative Approach

Regressors	B	S.E.	β	t	Sig.
(Constant)	1.963	.138		14.185	.000
knowledge	.084	.055	.113	1.536	.125
regulation	.287	.055	.385	5.244	.000*

$F(2, 368) = 54.805, p < 0.01, R^2 = 0.229, \Delta R^2 = 0.225$

Between the two indicators of metacognitive awareness, only regulation found to be significant predictor of overall attitude towards communicative approach among students; ($\beta = 0.287, t = 5.244, p < 0.01$). Knowledge was found to pose non-significant influence, such that the

beta value of 0.113 posed a t-statistics of 1.536 with p-value greater 0.05. To this effect, it is conclusive that regulation of cognition is the domain that best influences the attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students.

The study finds out that between the two indicators of metacognitive awareness, regulation of cognition is the variable that best influence the attitude towards communicative approach among Junior High School students. The relationship and immediate influence of regulation of cognition on attitude towards communicative approach as determined in this study confirms the arguments of several authors such who have reviewed the use of metacognitive strategies on the achievement of communicative approach in the classroom context and agree that there is a positive relationship between them. In learning process, self-regulation entails developing a plan to achieve a task-specific goal, monitoring and controlling one's ongoing performance, and self-reflection (Panadero, 2017). Self-regulated learning is an overarching construct that takes into consideration the influence of environmental factors and is comprised of several psychological concepts, such as motivation, emotion, and metacognition.

The results of the main problem of this study as mentioned in the preceding paragraph support the theoretical framework anchored on Russell's Theory of Knowledge who underpins metacognition which requires individuals to examine what information may be known beyond a reasonable doubt. It is intended to produce the insight that even the most self-evident assumptions in our daily lives must be reexamined in the face of severe uncertainty. There is much for students to learn in the context of education; therefore, the acquisition of knowledge should be an important objective of schooling. Russell views the formation of children and character as the primary objective of education. Character traits such as courage and intelligence are crucial for Russell in his pursuit of innovative learning ways to acquire knowledge in all subject areas. Consequently, communication abilities would suffer in the absence of knowledge. Moreover, Gopinath (2014) verifies the importance of metacognitive awareness in interpersonal interaction, reading comprehension, language acquisition, problem solving, and character formation.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are formulated based on the findings of the study. Hence, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative hypothesis based on the statistics result of the study. Moreover, a high level of metacognitive awareness and a moderate result of attitude towards communicative approach was discovered among the student-respondents of the research study. The research findings also show that there is a strong correlation between metacognitive awareness and attitude towards communicative approach. And besides, regulation of cognition is found to be the dominant predictor of attitude towards communicative approach.

Last but not least, the study's findings demonstrated that regulation of cognition of metacognitive awareness is the domain that most strongly influences the attitude

of Junior High School students toward communicative approach. Therefore, Russell's Theory of Knowledge concurs with the findings of metacognitive awareness of attitude in a communicative method in which knowledge is viewed as behavior and logic that facilitate learning. There is much for students to learn; therefore, acquiring knowledge should be a major objective of education. A basic cognitive relationship and fundamental feature of human experience is familiarity. A subject experience (perceives, reflects upon, recalls, or imagines) an object in the context of a subject-object relationship. In order for students to learn, they must be exposed to all linguistic activities.

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